

region corresponding to H_2O and or C—H in the compounds. This indicates the presence of water molecule in coordinated and H-bonded form². This also indicates the presence of pyridine molecules. The pyridine vibrations in the region of 1600 cm^{-1} to 400 cm^{-1} are very clear. However, some of the bands appear to have been mixed up due to the vibrational bands of the anions present in the compounds. Also, there are slight shiftings in the pyridine bands indicating coordination to metal ions. Similar shiftings have been found in many pyridine compounds by other workers³. Pyridine has a strong band at 750 cm^{-1} corresponding to out of plane C—H vibration⁴. This may be taken as an evidence for a weak bonding between pyridine and the metal ions in the compounds. There are medium bands also in the 1600 cm^{-1} region corresponding to H_2O mode of vibration. Aquo-complexes generally show vibrational band in this region⁵. The vibrational mode of coordinated water has been observed by several workers⁶⁻⁸ in the region of 800 cm^{-1} and the band is very weak. The infra-red data of the compounds indicates the presence of a weak band in this region corresponding to coordinated water molecules. These bands are observed at 820 cm^{-1} and 830 cm^{-1} in the compounds. Strong infra-red bands at 920 and 895 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of $CuMoO_4 \cdot 4Py \cdot 2H_2O$ may be due to MoO_4 -mode. Similarly a doubt at 640 cm^{-1} and a weak band at 660 cm^{-1} in its spectrum may have a major contribution from MoO_4 . The strong broad absorption at 790 cm^{-1} may also have contribution from MoO_4 . On comparison of I.R. spectrum of this compound with that of $Cu(VO_3)_2 \cdot Py \cdot 3H_2O$, it appears that there is a new strong band at 820 cm^{-1} and very broad bands at 590 cm^{-1} and 525 cm^{-1} . As these bands⁹ are present only in the spectrum of $Cu(VO_3)_2 \cdot Py \cdot 3H_2O$, they may be assigned to VO_3 group. The presence of a broad absorption hump in the region of $1000-700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the infra-red spectrum of $CuWO_4 \cdot Py$ may be due to WO_4 vibrations. Since there is no such absorption in the spectra of any of the other compounds mentioned here, it appears that this assignment is reasonable. There is a medium band in the region of 1600 cm^{-1} in the I.R. spectra of the compounds suggesting coordinated water molecule⁵. On this basis the compound may also be thought to be as $CuWO_4 \cdot Py \cdot H_2O$ instead of $CuWO_4 \cdot Py$, as suggested on the basis of elemental analysis.

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Synthesis of Oxovanadium(IV) Complexes with Some New Tridentate Schiff Bases

A. SYAMAL*, K. S. KALE and S. BANERJEE†

Department of Applied Sciences and Humanities, Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra 132 119, Haryana

and

Department of Chemistry, Regional Engineering College, Kurukshetra 132 119, Haryana

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THE metal complexes of tridentate dibasic ligands usually exhibit novel magnetic, spectral and structural properties¹⁻⁴. The dibasic behaviour of these ligands forces the metal (II and III) ions to dimerise or polymerise leading to metal complexes with unusual magnetic properties. In recent years there has been considerable interest on the syntheses and magnetic properties of copper(II) and oxovanadium(IV) complexes of tridentate ONO donor dibasic Schiff bases derived from salicylaldehyde or substituted salicylaldehyde and orthoaminophenol⁵⁻⁷. In this preliminary communication we report the synthesis of several new oxovanadium(IV) complexes of Schiff bases derived from salicylaldehyde or substituted salicylaldehyde and orthoaminobenzylalcohol. It may be mentioned that this is the first report on the metal complexes of these ligands and we wish to make a comprehensive study of the coordination complexes of these ligands with various transition and non-transition metal ions.

General Method of Synthesis of the Complexes :

A methanolic solution (50 ml) of the appropriate ligand prepared *in situ* was reacted with a methanolic solution of freshly prepared oxovanadium(IV) acetate under reflux with stirring. The separated precipitates were filtered, washed with methanol and dried under vacuum. The analytical data of the complexes are presented in Table 1.

The absence of the $\nu(OH)$ stretch in the infra-red spectra of the complexes indicates the deprotonation of the ligands and dibasic character of these ligands. The $\nu(V=O)$ frequency of the complexes occurs at

* For correspondence

† Dept. of Chemistry, Institute of Science, Bombay-400032

TABLE 1

Complex ^(a)		% V	% N	$\nu(V=O)$ cm ⁻¹
VO(sal-o aminobenzyl- alcohol)	Found	17.0	4.6	980
	Reqd.	17.47	4.79	
VO(5-br. mosal-o-amino- benzylalcohol)	Found	18.1	4.0	925
	Reqd.	18.75	3.77	
VO(5-methoxysal-o- aminobenzylalcohol)	Found	16.2	4.5	985
	Reqd.	15.84	4.35	
VO(3-ethoxysal-o- aminobenzylalcohol)	Found	15.4	4.2	925
	Reqd.	15.18	4.17	
VO(hydrox-o-aminobenzyl- alcohol)	Found	14.5	4.0	925
	Reqd.	14.91	4.09	

(a) Abbreviations: sal=salicylaldehyde, 5-bromosal=5-bromosalicylaldehyde, 5-methoxysal=5-methoxysalicylaldehyde, 3-ethoxysal=3-ethoxysalicylaldehyde and hydrox=2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde.

925-985 cm⁻¹ (see Table 1) and is in the usual range observed for many oxovanadium(IV) complexes⁸. The complexes are insoluble in common solvents and melt or decompose >250°. As the complexes are insoluble in common solvents it was not possible to find out molecular weights and degree of polymerisation of the complexes. The room temperature magnetic moments of the complexes as determined by the Gouy method using Hg[Co(NCS)₄] as a standard are in the range 1.3-1.5 B.M. The observed magnetic moments of the complexes are less than the spin-only moment of 1.73 B.M. expected for an S=½ system, which are attributed to the antiferromagnetic spin-spin exchange between the interacting VO²⁺ ions⁷, as are the cases with the oxovanadium(IV) complexes of comparable ligands⁶.

The ESR and cryomagnetic studies on the complexes are in progress and details will be reported in due course. The corresponding copper(II) complexes are also being studied in order to compare the magnetic behaviour of these S=½ systems.

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A Rapid Gravimetric Method for the Determination and Separation of Cadmium

(Miss) A. GUHA THAKURTA, B. DAS* and S. C. SHOME

Chemical Laboratory, Presidency College, Calcutta

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CADMIUM has been determined gravimetrically with a number of organic precipitants, but only a few of them¹⁻⁵ produce complexes suitable for direct weighing. In the present investigation 3-hydroxy 1,3-diphenyl triazine (HDPTA)⁶⁻⁸, a N-substituted phenylhydroxamic acid, has been employed for the direct determination of cadmium in small concentrations with a good degree of accuracy and for separation of the metal from a large number of diverse ions. The bright yellow precipitate of cadmium is obtained from solutions at pH 6.7-8.2 with HDPTA which is finely granular in texture and insoluble in hot water or 30% ethanol. The complex has been found to have the composition Cd(C₁₂H₁₀N₃O)₂.

Experimental

A solution of cadmium nitrate was prepared and standardised by the molybdate method. Solutions of diverse ions were prepared by dissolving known amounts of their pure compounds in water; dilute acids were added wherever necessary. The reagent (HDPTA) was prepared in the laboratory by the reaction between phenylhydroxylamine and benzene-diazonium chloride. A fresh 1% solution of recrystallized reagent in 95% ethanol was used for precipitation of cadmium.

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade.

Procedure: A known aliquot of cadmium solution (6-41 mg of Cd) was taken in a beaker, diluted to 150 ml, 5-25 ml of the reagent solution were added into it dropwise and the pH was raised to 6.7-8.2 by adding 3M ammonia solution with constant stirring. The cadmium complex formed was allowed to settle at room temperature for 15-20 minutes with occasional stirring. The precipitate was filtered on a sintered bed glass crucible (No. 3), washed with warm (50°) 30% ethanol, dried at 110° and weighed to constant weight. The gravimetric factor used for the metal was 0.2089.

For complete precipitation of cadmium as the complex, at least 1.25 times the theoretical amount of the reagent was required. Use of large excess of the reagent produced high results.

Separation of Cadmium from Diverse Ions: Cadmium was precipitated with HDPTA in presence of Zn²⁺, Al³⁺, Sb³⁺, Bi³⁺ and As⁵⁺ using tartrate as

* Dept. of Agril. Chem. and Soil Science, B. C. K. V. V., Kalyani, West Bengal.